

Short name	London Protocol	Long name	Contracting Party to the London Protocol
Geographic scope	International + national		
Description of how this issue tends to manifest (include footnotes for key references)	<p>The London Protocol prohibits the dumping of wastes and other matter in the marine environment. In 2006, the Contracting Parties to the London Protocol adopted amendments to Annex 1 to allow for CO₂ storage, thereby creating a legal basis in international environmental law to regulate CO₂ storage in sub-seabed geological formations. In 2009, article 6 was amended to allow export of CO₂ for storage in sub-seabed geological formations, with the introduction of a new paragraph. The new paragraph, 6.2, makes clear that Contracting Parties need an agreement or arrangement to transport CO₂. The amendment is not in force awaiting a sufficient number of ratifications. The 2019 resolution sought to accelerate the operationalization of the amendment and allow states to provisionally apply the 2009 amendment, provided they have deposited a formal declaration of provisional application to IMO.</p>		
Key examples where this issue manifests (also based on stakeholder inputs)	<p>This issue poses a necessary condition for the legality of CO₂ storage offshore.</p> <p>The agreement or arrangement must include a confirmation and allocation of permitting responsibilities between the exporting and receiving countries, consistent with the provisions of the protocol, and international law. In the case of export to a non-Contracting Party, the agreement or arrangement must contain provisions at a minimum equivalent to those contained in the London Protocol.</p>		
Other issues this affects			
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International Maritime Organization. (1996). Protocol to the Convention on the Prevention of Marine Pollution by Dumping of Waste and Other Matter 1972. • International Maritime Organization. (n.d.). Guidance on the implementation of article 6.2 on the export of CO₂ streams for disposal in sub-seabed geological formations for the purpose of sequestration. Available on the IMO website: https://www.imo.org/en/OurWork/Environment/PollutionPrevention/Garbage/Documents/LC%2035-15%20Annex%206.pdf • International Maritime Organization. (2006). Resolution LP.1(1) (Adopted on 2 November 2006) on the Amendment to Include CO₂ Sequestration in sub-seabed geological formation in Annex 1 to the London Protocol. 		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"><li data-bbox="443 188 1406 309">• International Maritime Organization. (2009). Resolution LP.3(4) (Adopted on 30 October 2009) on the amendment to Article 6 of the London Protocol.<li data-bbox="443 353 1406 468">• International Maritime Organization. (2019). Resolution LP.5(14) (Adopted on 11 October 2019) on the Provisional Application of the 2009 Amendment to Article 6 of the London Protocol.
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